

AGE-SPECIFIC CHANGES IN THE INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation

The article discusses the main characteristic of the age of physical development indicators of preschool children

Key words

Physical development, sports, physical qualities, movement, coordination, optimal, exercise, competition, ability

The physical development of preschool children is a continuous process that has its own characteristics. One of them is its unevenness. We are talking about the undulating growth of the baby, which then increases, then vice versa, slows down for a while. The child grows most intensively from birth to one year old. During this period, it increases by about 25-40 cm, gaining 50% of body weight at birth.

After birth, the child has poorly developed muscles, which make up only one fourth of the total body weight. The muscle fibers are unnaturally thin, but as the child grows, they strengthen and increase in volume.

The development of muscle motor ability begins with the muscles in the neck, after which the muscles of the body and limbs are connected to the process. From one year to three years old, the baby learns the basic movements, the nervous system matures, and now the child confidently walks, runs, plays with the ball. In order for motor activity to develop correctly, it is necessary from birth not to limit the child's freedom of action and participate in the process of strengthening his muscles.

At preschool age, children experience ossification of cartilage tissues, but bones are still not strong enough. That is why, before the final strengthening of bones (that is, until the age of 12), it is necessary to protect the baby from participating in power sports.

The development of the skeleton is directly related to the development of ligaments, muscles and joints. As a child grows older, his muscle mass also increases in volume and by the end of preschool age it is approaching 27% of the

total body weight. It is important to monitor how the child walks and sits in order to eliminate possible problems with posture in the future.

Nutrition is of great importance at this age. The child should receive enough protein food, as well as the necessary amount of foods with a high content of calcium and magnesium, which will positively affect the strengthening of bone tissues.

Preschool children are too mobile and restless. Movements are fast and impulsive, and attention is unstable, due to the fact that the processes of arousal prevail over the processes of inhibition. As a result, the load on the cardiovascular and respiratory systems increases.

Special attention is paid to the development of fine motor skills, finger games are used in gaming activities. Such classes are emotional, exciting, and contribute to the development of speech and creative activity of children. Many games require the participation of both hands, which makes it possible to develop spatial representations (up-down, back — front). Finger games selected in the program are necessary for the development of creative imagination of preschoolers.

The physical development of D.V. Khukhlaeva is defined as the process of development of a set of morphological and functional properties of the body (growth rate, body weight gain, a certain sequence of increase in various parts of the body, their proportions, maturation of various organs, systems at a certain stage of development), mainly programmed by hereditary mechanisms and implemented according to a certain plan under optimal conditions of vital activity .

Physical development, according to V.I. Kozlov, is also a continuously occurring biological process. At each age, these processes differ in a set of functional, morphological, mental and other properties of the body related to each other, with the external environment, which are due to the reserve of physical strength. Heredity, the environment, socio-economic factors, nutrition, physical activity, sports – all this affects the physical development of a person.

The level of physical development determines the indicators of physical fitness, muscular, and mental performance of a person.

Physical development is characterized by changes in three groups of indicators:

1) body composition indicators – body length, body weight, posture, volumes and shapes of individual body parts – they characterize the biological forms (morphology) of a person;

2) health indicators – reflect morphological and functional changes in the physiological systems of the human body (the work of all organs and systems of the body);

3) indicators of the development of physical qualities (strength, speed abilities, endurance, etc.) .

These indicators, changing over the course of a person's life, determine the nature of his physical development. Effective management of physical development is carried out taking into account the patterns of changes in body composition, health and physical qualities.

J.K. Kholodov, V.S. Kuznetsov define the laws that govern the process of physical development. These laws include:

- the laws of heredity as the ability of organisms to transmit their characteristics and developmental features to offspring, so that all living beings retain the characteristic features of the species in their descendants; these laws should be taken into account as factors that favor or hinder the physical improvement of a person (heredity is taken into account when predicting athletic achievements);

- the law of age gradation – intervention in the process of physical development of a person to manage it is possible on the basis of taking into account the characteristics and capabilities of the human body at various age stages;

- the law of the unity of the organism and the environment – was formulated and justified by I.M. Sechenov in 1861, developed by I.P. Pavlov – assumes consideration of human living conditions – social conditions, working conditions, everyday life, education and others, which affects the physical condition of the human body, changes in its functions, forms; The geographical environment also affects physical development;

Taking into account these laws allows for an effective and scientifically sound approach to the consideration and organization of the process of human physical development.

In the aspect of physical development, it is necessary to consider such concepts as physical qualities, physical education.

Physical qualities are understood as socially conditioned aggregates of biological and mental properties of a person, expressing his physical readiness to carry out active motor activity. The physical qualities of a person include strength, speed, flexibility, dexterity, endurance. Strength is the ability to overcome external resistance due to the effort of muscle fibers. Speed is the

ability to perform a movement in the shortest possible time. Dexterity – the ability to quickly rebuild motor activity and perform complex coordination movements, includes the ability to create new motor skills, the ability to quickly respond to a change in the situation and the ability to perform complex coordination movements. Flexibility is the ability to perform movements with maximum amplitude, which depends on the morphofunctional features of the motor apparatus, muscle viscosity, ligament elasticity, the condition of the intervertebral discs. Endurance is the ability to perform long-term work and resist fatigue. There are several types of endurance: static, dynamic, speed-power, local, regional. In sports fights, under equal conditions, it is endurance that can become the defining quality of the winner.

Preschool age is the period of a child's life of 3-7 years. According to A.N. Leontiev, it is the period of the "initial actual folding" of personality, the time of formation of personal mechanisms and formations, the period of intensive physical development of the child. A similar opinion is held by J.K.Xolodov, noting that at preschool age all the most important functions and systems of the body are intensively developing. In the same age period, the foundations for the comprehensive development of the child's physical abilities are laid. Tempering, mastering motor skills, hygiene skills, etc. are most favorable at preschool age..

The tasks of physical development of children are:

- 1) formation of children's need for physical activity, development of interest in participating in joint outdoor games and physical exercises;
- 2) the development of physical qualities in children – speed, strength, as well as endurance, coordination, flexibility;
- 3) preservation and strengthening of children's physical and mental health;
- 4) formation of children's initial ideas about a healthy lifestyle.

In no other period of life is physical development so closely linked to general development as in the first six years. During preschool childhood, the foundations of health, longevity, comprehensive motor fitness and harmonious physical development are laid in the child. The outstanding teacher V.A. Sukhomlinsky emphasized that their spiritual life, worldview, mental development, strength in knowledge, and self-confidence depend on the health and cheerfulness of children. Therefore, it is extremely important to organize physical education classes in childhood, which will allow the body to accumulate strength and ensure further comprehensive harmonious development of the personality.

During outdoor activities, at different air temperatures in appropriate clothes, the child's body defenses and metabolic processes in it increase.

The simplest tourism. This is an important means of physical education. Excursions and walks outside the preschool are carried out with children regularly starting from the first younger group, taking into account their age characteristics and capabilities, health status, location of the preschool institution. The most favorable season for long walks is summer. Walking allows you to introduce children to various children's and physical education institutions located near the preschool.

In the older preschool age, children already have quite a lot of motor experience, which allows them to conduct the simplest hiking trips.

At the preparatory stage, thematic conversations are held with children. The teacher reads them fiction of appropriate content, shows them slides and tourist equipment. An important place at this stage is given to story-role-playing games, in which the child is taught how to pack a backpack, how to behave in the forest, and how to navigate the terrain.

Hiking trips are aimed at promoting physical culture and sports. They can also be of a local history nature, their purpose is to broaden the horizons and consolidate the knowledge of children about their native land, foster respect for nature.

Despite the diverse content of hiking trips, in all their variants, it is necessary to correctly combine cognitive and motor activity, cultivate strong-willed qualities in overcoming difficulties, develop self-control, perseverance, good relationships, mutual assistance and mutual assistance .

Thus, physical development is manageable. With the help of physical exercises, various sports, rational nutrition, tempering, work and rest, various indicators of physical development can be changed in the necessary direction.

Having considered in the second chapter the methods and means of education used in the process of forming the physical development of preschool children, it was concluded that in order to ensure the maximum physical development of each child, it is necessary to fulfill a number of conditions:

1. Selection of adequate teaching tools and methods;
2. The creative orientation of the pedagogical process;
3. The use, along with traditional forms of work (morning gymnastics, physical education classes, outdoor games and exercises, physical education

leisure, sports holidays), of non-traditional means and methods of education, such as rhythmic gymnastics, exercise equipment, sports dancing, etc.

During the study of methods of physical development of preschool children, two groups of methods were identified by analyzing literary sources: specific, general pedagogical E.Ya. Stepanenkova.

In these methods, various means can be used, such as story exercises, outdoor games, sports exercises, simple tourism, etc.

Thus, the most important role in the physical development of a child still belongs to educators and instructors. It is their ability to methodically organize and conduct classes correctly, non-standard approaches to choosing forms, methods and means of conducting them that are the most important components of developing interest in classes, forming necessary habits, motor skills and abilities in a child.

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